

A kinetic study of nonthermal plasma pyrolysis of methane: Insights into hydrogen and carbon material production

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ABSTRACT

Nonthermal plasma-assisted methane pyrolysis has emerged as a promising approach for hydrogen production under mild conditions while simultaneously yielding valuable carbon materials. Herein, we develop a plasma chemical kinetic model to elucidate the underlying reaction mechanisms involved in methane pyrolysis to hydrogen and solid carbon within a gliding arc (GA) reactor. A zero-dimensional (0D) chemical kinetics model was developed to simulate the plasma chemistry during the GA-based methane pyrolysis process, incorporating reactions involving electrons, excited species, ions, and heavy species. The model accurately predicted methane conversion and product selectivity in agreement with the experimental data. A strong correlation between hydrogen production and methane conversion was observed, primarily driven by the reaction $\text{CH}_4 + \text{H} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3 + \text{H}_2$, contributing 44.2% to hydrogen formation and 37.7% to methane depletion. Electron impact collisions with hydrocarbons play a secondary role, accounting for 31.1% of H_2 formation. This work provides a detailed investigation into the mechanism of solid carbon formation in GA-assisted methane pyrolysis. Most of the solid carbon originates from the electron impact dissociation of C_2H_2 through reactions $\text{e} + \text{C}_2\text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{e} + \text{C}_2 + \text{H}_2/2\text{H}$ and subsequent C_2 condensation. C_2 radicals are highlighted as the major contributors to solid carbon formation, accounting for 95.0% of the total carbon yield, which might be due to the relatively low C–H dissociation energy in C_2H_2 . This kinetic study offers a comprehensive understanding of the mechanisms behind H_2 and solid carbon formation during GA-assisted methane pyrolysis.

1. Introduction

Hydrogen (H_2) is increasingly recognized as a versatile energy carrier with the potential to play a pivotal role in achieving net-zero emissions. Its high energy density and clean combustion make it a promising alternative to fossil fuels in various sectors, including transportation, industry, and power generation [1,2]. However, the majority of hydrogen production today (70–80%) relies on steam reforming of natural gas, followed by the water–gas shift reaction, which results in substantial carbon dioxide emissions [3]. This conventional method contributes significantly to greenhouse gas emissions and hinders efforts to mitigate climate change. To address these environmental concerns, there is a growing emphasis on developing and deploying low-carbon hydrogen production pathways. Water electrolysis, often referred to as green hydrogen if powered by renewable energy, and methane pyrolysis, which produces turquoise hydrogen, are emerging as promising

technologies in this transition. These methods offer the potential to produce hydrogen without generating direct carbon dioxide emissions, making them crucial for decarbonizing the energy sector.

Methane pyrolysis offers distinct advantages over water electrolysis because of its lower energy demand (only 37 kJ/mol for H_2 production, compared to 286 kJ/mol for water electrolysis) and cogeneration of valuable solid carbon. However, conventional thermal methane pyrolysis demands extremely high temperatures, exceeding 1000 °C, to overcome the strong C–H bond energy of 4.5 eV in methane molecules, resulting in high energy consumption [4,5]. Additionally, the thermal methane pyrolysis process typically requires significant capital investment and often involves the use of catalysts. However, these catalysts are susceptible to deactivation, and separating carbon from spent catalysts remains a challenge. In contrast, nonthermal plasma (NTP) can activate inert CH_4 molecules through highly energetic electrons under ambient conditions. Mild operating conditions offer additional

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advantages, including rapid start-up and shutdown; decentralized flexibility; lower capital expenditure; and flexibility in process design, integration, and operation. This flexibility makes NTP-based methane pyrolysis particularly suitable for integration with renewable energy sources, such as wind and solar power. Additionally, biomethane, derived from the anaerobic digestion of organic waste, can also be a suitable feedstock for methane pyrolysis, potentially achieving negative carbon emissions.

NTP technology, particularly gliding arcs (GAs), has attracted increased interest for methane pyrolysis due to its relatively high energy efficiency compared to that of other types of NTP, such as dielectric barrier discharge (DBD). Zhang et al. [6,7] utilized a GA reactor to produce hydrogen from a highly diluted CH₄/N₂ mixture (CH₄/N₂ = 0.1), achieving a maximum CH₄ conversion of 91.8% but incurring a high energy cost of 48.8 kWh/kg (H₂). They also elucidated the dominant reaction pathways leading to the loss of H₂ and hydrocarbons. Wang et al. [8] reported the production of graphene nanoflakes using He and H₂ as carrier gases in a magnetically stabilized GA reactor. Wu et al. [9] developed a rotating gliding arc (RGA) for the conversion of methane into H₂ and carbon aerosols using N₂ and Ar as carrier gases. Transparent crumpled-like graphene sheets and spherical nanostructured carbon were observed for both the CH₄/Ar and CH₄/N₂ discharges. Heijckers et al. [10] compared direct methane conversion to H₂ and hydrocarbons in different types of NTP systems, including DBD, microwave plasma and RGA, highlighting the predominant role of thermal conversion over vibrational-translational nonequilibrium when using RGA and microwave plasma systems. Raja et al. [11] explored direct methane pyrolysis to H₂ and solid carbon using a novel swirl-induced point-plane discharge reactor, focusing on the effect of the methane flow rate on the product yield and selectivity. The authors achieved the highest methane conversion (19.7%) with a 16% hydrogen yield and a 51.5 kWh/kg (H₂) energy cost at 0.5 L/min.

While NTP technology offers a promising avenue for converting methane into hydrogen and solid carbon, NTP-based methane pyrolysis still faces a number of challenges. First, the energy consumption of hydrogen production via NTP methane pyrolysis remains relatively high compared to that associated with steam reforming of natural gas combined with carbon capture and storage. Second, most studies on NTP methane pyrolysis have used highly diluted methane with inert carrier gases such as argon, helium, and nitrogen, which is different from industrial practices where pure methane is often used. Third, most related research has focused on the production of hydrogen and hydrocarbons (especially C₂ hydrocarbons), with limited attention given to the formation and characterization of solid carbon. Solid carbon, a byproduct of methane pyrolysis, has significant commercial value due to its versatility. It can be produced in various forms, including carbon black, graphite, graphene, and carbon nanotubes, each with distinct properties and applications. Therefore, substantial research efforts are essential to advance NTP-based methane pyrolysis technology for the cogeneration of H₂ and carbon materials. A comprehensive understanding of the underlying reaction mechanisms for direct methane pyrolysis into hydrogen and solid carbon under NTP conditions is crucial. In particular, elucidating the pathways leading to solid carbon formation is paramount. Addressing this critical knowledge gap is important in optimizing process parameters, enhancing reaction performance, and developing robust reactor designs, ultimately facilitating the scale-up of NTP-based methane pyrolysis for industrial applications.

In this study, direct methane pyrolysis for the cogeneration of H₂ and carbon materials was investigated using a conventional GA reactor. Comprehensive characterization of the produced carbon materials was carried out to obtain a better understanding of their properties. A novel zero-dimensional (0D) chemical kinetics model was developed to investigate the plasma chemistry involved in this process, with a particular focus on the formation of solid carbon and hydrogen. This marks the first detailed investigation into the formation pathways of solid carbon in NTP-based methane pyrolysis. The accuracy of the model

was validated by comparing the calculated methane conversion and product selectivity with experimental results obtained at various flow rates. This model enables a detailed elucidation of plasma chemistry and reaction pathways, including the formation of two primary carbon species (C and C₂), during NTP methane pyrolysis.

2. Experimental methods and kinetic modeling

2.1. Experimental setup

Fig. 1 shows a schematic of the experimental setup used in this study. Two diverging stainless-steel electrodes, each 60 mm in length and 18 mm in width, were positioned 3 mm downstream of the nozzle exit with a minimum discharge gap of 2 mm. An AC high-voltage neon transformer supplied power to the plasma system, delivering a maximum peak-to-peak voltage of 10 kV at a fixed frequency of 50 Hz. The arc voltage was measured using a high-voltage probe (Testec, TT-HVP 15 HF), while the arc current was recorded using a current monitor (Magnetlab CT-E0.5). A four-channel digital oscilloscope (Tektronix, MDO3024) was used to sample both electrical signals.

Pure CH₄ (BOC, zero grade) was used as the feed gas and was regulated using a mass flow controller (Omega, FMA-2404) before introduction into the GA reactor. The solid carbon produced during the process was collected in a downstream vessel. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images of the carbon materials were recorded using a multipurpose transmission electron microscope (JEOL, JEM-2100+). X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the carbon samples were obtained using an automated X-ray diffractometer (Rigaku, SmartLab) equipped with nickel-filtered Cu K α radiation. The data were collected in the 2 θ range of 5° to 90° at a scan rate of 4°/min. Diffraction peaks were identified by comparison with reference patterns in the JCPDS database. Raman analysis was conducted using a compact Raman spectrometer (Renshaw, RM-2000) equipped with a laser at an excitation wavelength of 514 nm. The gas products were analyzed using a gas chromatograph (Shimadzu, GC-2014) instrument equipped with a flame ionization detector and a thermal conductivity detector. The gas chromatograph was calibrated with standard calibration gas mixtures to ensure accuracy. All the measurements were repeated three times to ensure reliability, with a margin of error maintained within 3%.

The conversion of CH₄ (X_{CH_4}) was calculated using the following equation:

$$X_{CH_4}(\%) = \frac{CH_4 \text{ converted (mol/s)}}{CH_4 \text{ input (mol/s)}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

The selectivity of the gas products was determined as follows:

$$S_{H_2}(\%) = \frac{2 \times H_2 \text{ produced (mol/s)}}{4 \times CH_4 \text{ converted (mol/s)}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

$$S_{C_xH_y}(\%) = \frac{x \times C_xH_y \text{ produced (mol/s)}}{CH_4 \text{ converted (mol/s)}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

$$S_{\text{carbon}}(\%) = 100 - S_{C_xH_y} \quad (4)$$

The discharge power (P) of the GA was determined by the integral of the arc voltage multiplied by the arc current:

$$P(W) = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^{t=T} U(t) \times I(t) dt \quad (5)$$

The specific energy input (SEI) is given by:

$$SEI(\text{kWh/m}^3) = \frac{P \text{ (kW)}}{\text{Total flow rate (m}^3/\text{h)}} \quad (6)$$

The energy cost of hydrogen production (EC_{H_2}) is defined as follows:

$$EC_{H_2}(\text{kWh/kg H}_2) = \frac{SEI \text{ (kWh/m}^3)}{\text{produced H}_2 \text{ (kg/m}^3)} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the experimental setup.

The energy efficiency of CH₄ conversion (η_{Con}) and the fuel production efficiency (FPE) of the plasma process were calculated as follows:

$$\eta_{\text{Con}}(\text{g/kWh}) = \frac{\text{Converted CH}_4 (\text{g/m}^3)}{\text{SEI} (\text{kWh/m}^3)} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{FPE}(\%) = \frac{\sum \text{Fuel produced} (\text{mol/s}) \times \text{LHV} (\text{kJ/mol})}{\text{CH}_4 \text{ converted} (\text{mol/s}) \times \text{LHV of CH}_4 (\text{kJ/mol}) + \text{Discharge power} (\text{kW})} \times 100 \quad (9)$$

where LHV is the low heating value of the fuel, as shown in Table 1.

2.2. Numerical methods and kinetic models

A 0D plasma-kinetic model was developed using the open-source ZDPlasKin code [13] to investigate the underlying methane pyrolysis mechanism in the GA reactor. Key discharge characteristics, including a reduced electric field and residence time, were incorporated into the model through a simplified representation of temporal and spatial power dissipation. Kinetic simulation was used to compute the time-dependent evolution of the densities of individual species. In this study, we assume a uniform plasma environment and do not consider

Table 1
The LHV of different fuels (kJ/mol, 25 °C) [12].

Fuel	CH ₄	C ₂ H ₂	C ₂ H ₄	C ₂ H ₆	C ₃ H ₈	C ₄ H ₁₀	H ₂
LHV	802.8	1255.8	1322.0	1431.7	2043.2	2657.5	242.3

the complexities of real plasma reactors, such as localized hotspots, temperature gradients, and variations in electron density.

During a typical GA cycle, an arc is initially ignited at the narrowest gap between the electrodes. Driven by high gas flow, the arc moves along the electrodes, extending its length until it extinguishes. It subsequently reignites at the narrowest discharge gap, repeating the cycle [14]. GAs are characterized by complex gas-arc interactions and stochastic discharge behavior and are frequently involved in regular igni-

tion, motion and extinction cycles [15]. These factors complicate the theoretical calculation of plasma properties in a GA. Therefore, the following approximations were made to simplify the simulation. The GA was described as a plasma column with a radius of 0.5 mm based on previous simulations [15,16]. The arc was assumed to move consistently with the gas flow, so the arc length was simplified to the average length of the discharge gap. The quenching time was taken from the electrical waveforms (see Figure S1 and S2 in the Supporting Information (SI)) in this study using a method similar to that used in a previous study [17]. The gas temperature and electric field inside the GA were assumed to be spatially uniform. The gas temperature was assumed to be 1,000 K according to [18]. The average electric field (E) was calculated from the power density using the so-called local field approximation [19]:

$$E = \sqrt{\frac{P}{V_{\text{discharge}} \times \sigma}} \quad (8)$$

where $V_{\text{discharge}}$ is the discharge volume (m³). In our model, the discharge power was assumed to be uniform both temporally and

spatially. σ is the plasma conductivity ($\text{A V}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$), calculated from Equation 9.

$$\sigma = e \times n_e \times \mu_e \quad (9)$$

where n_e is the electron number density and μ_e is the electron mobility. All of these values were calculated by BOLSIG+ [20].

A 0D chemical kinetic model was developed to solve a set of continuity equations for each species in our simulation, as detailed in Section 2 of the SI. This model includes neutral–neutral reactions, electron-impact reactions, and reactions involving vibrationally excited species and ions. The chemistry set for the interactions between neutral species was primarily built upon the work of Sun et al. [21–23] due to their excellent prediction ability. The rate coefficients for electron-impact collisions were determined using BOLSIG+ [20] and integrated into ZDPlasKin. Electron collision cross-sections for H_2 and CH_3 and vibrational excitation of CH_4 , C_2H_2 , C_2H_4 , C_2H_6 , and C_3H_8 were obtained from the LXCat online database [24]. The electron collision cross sections for C_1 – C_3 hydrocarbon dissociation and ionization were calculated using the method proposed by Janev & Reiter [25].

A detailed mechanism for vibrational kinetics and ionic chemistry was also considered. The vibrational-translational (VT) energy exchange processes were incorporated using the parameters from [26], while the rate coefficients for vibrational-vibrational (VV) energy transfer were obtained from [27]. The reaction rate constants for interactions between vibrationally excited species and radicals were determined using the Fridman-Macheret α -Model [28]. In total, the kinetic model included 57 species and 604 reactions for GA-based methane cracking. Specifically, this model includes a pathway for solid carbon formation, in addition to the conventional kinetic data of methane pyrolysis. The formation of solid carbon begins with a condensation process involving reactive species, particularly carbon radicals such as C and C_2 derived from CH_4 decomposition [29,30]. These radicals become the foundation for subsequent carbon deposition [31]. Therefore, the model includes two types of carbon species, C and C_2 , and considers 53 carbon-related reactions. Additionally, the model accounts for the deposition of these carbon species, highlighting that once carbon undergoes condensation, it is effectively protected from plasma-induced decomposition. Surface reactions at the arc footprint contribute to carbon formation in the GA [32]. However, we could only model carbon deposition in a uniform plasma volume due to the lack of detailed surface kinetic data and the limitations of the 0D model.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Reaction performance and validation of the model

Model validation was achieved by comparing the simulation results with the experimental data. Fig. 2 shows good agreement between the experimental and simulation data for various flow rates. The model effectively predicted both the values and trends of CH_4 conversion, product selectivity and energy cost for H_2 production as a function of flow rate. Fig. 2(a) shows that CH_4 conversion decreased from 7.0% to 4.2% as the flow rate increased from 3.5 to 5.5 L/min. This result is attributed to the reduced residence time of reactants within the discharge zone at higher flow rates (Figure S2), which limits the exposure of CH_4 molecules to the reactive species necessary for effective conversion [33]. In contrast, the energy cost for hydrogen production exhibited a more complex relationship with the flow rate. The energy cost initially decreased as the flow rate increased and then increased as the flow rate approached 5.5 L/min, reaching a minimum (20.2 kWh/kg H_2) at a gas flow rate of 4.5 L/min, outperforming most previous gliding arc reactors (40–50 kWh/kg H_2) [11,34,35]. The FPE and energy efficiency of CH_4 conversion followed trends similar to those of the energy cost of H_2 production, achieving optimal values of 83.2% and 255.4 g/kWh, respectively, at a gas flow rate of 4.5 L/min, as illustrated in

Fig. 2. Measured and calculated CH_4 conversion, product selectivity and energy cost as a function of CH_4 flow rate at a constant discharge power of 45 W.

Figure S3 in the SI.

Fig. 2(b) compares the simulated and experimental selectivities of the main products at various flow rates, revealing excellent agreement with a relative error below 15.3%. Hydrogen was the primary product, exceeding 60% selectivity, followed by higher-chain hydrocarbons (C_2H_2 , C_2H_6 , and C_3H_8) and solid carbon. Increasing the gas flow rate generally enhanced the selectivity of hydrogen from 72.3% to 78.3%. This increasing trend in hydrogen selectivity with flow rate is consistent with findings from previous studies using needle-to-plate and GA reactors [36,37].

Additionally, the effect of discharge power on reaction performance was also examined by increasing the discharge power from 25 to 65 W while maintaining a constant total flow rate of 4.5 L/min. Increasing the discharge power nearly tripled the methane conversion, from 2.3% to 6.7%, and increased the selectivities for H_2 , C_2H_2 , and solid carbon (Figure S5). However, the increase in discharge power from 45 to 65 W led to a decrease in the energy efficiency of CH_4 conversion and FPE (see Figure S4 in the SI).

Solid carbon is one of the most important products of GA-based methane pyrolysis, achieving 24.4% selectivity under optimal

Fig. 3. Representative TEM images of carbon nanomaterials produced via GA-based CH_4 pyrolysis: (a)(b) Overall morphology of the aggregated carbons at lower magnification (scale bar 200, 100 nm); (c)(d) Morphology of the carbon particles at medium magnification (scale bar 50, 10 nm); (e)(f) Graphitic/CNT nature at higher magnification (scale bar 50, 10 nm) (discharge power 45 W, CH_4 flow rate 4.5 L/min).

operation conditions (4.5 L/min, 45 W). Comprehensive characterization of the solid carbon was performed using TEM, XRD, and Raman spectroscopy. The TEM images (Fig. 3) reveal the formation of various carbon materials, including carbon black, graphite, graphene and multiwall carbon nanotubes. Fig. 3(a) and (b) present the overall morphology of the aggregated carbon materials, revealing their clustered arrangement. Fig. 3(c) and (e) show carbon nanoparticles with diameters ranging from 20 to 50 nm, demonstrating their uniform distribution. In Fig. 3(d) and (f), the ordered domains within the larger aggregates are evident, providing insight into the structural organization of the carbon materials. Specifically, Fig. 3(d) displays the graphitic layers of the samples at higher magnification, clearly showing the

production of abundant graphite characterized by a layer spacing of approximately 0.3 nm. This form of graphite is increasingly sought after for various promising industrial applications, such as battery anodes [38]. Moreover, the TEM images reveal the presence of multiwall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs), as shown in Fig. 3(f). These MWCNTs, with diameters ranging from 2–3 nm, grow in parallel mode and share the same wall. The wall thickness of these MWCNTs is approximately 0.3 nm, while the diameter of the hollow core is approximately 2 nm. A more detailed description of these carbon materials, including Raman and XRD results, can be found in Section 6 of the SI.

Table 2 compares the carbon materials produced by various methane pyrolysis methods, each of which has unique characteristics that influence the type and value of carbon materials produced. Thermal catalysis, for instance, can generate higher-value carbon materials, such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and carbon nanofibers (CNFs), when a suitable catalyst, such as an Fe-based catalyst, is employed [39]. CNTs and CNFs are highly valued for their superior mechanical, electrical, and thermal properties, making them attractive for advanced applications such as reinforced composites, conductive materials, and energy storage devices. Molten salt pyrolysis, on the other hand, produces different carbon materials depending on the salts used. With molten gallium, the process primarily yields carbon black [40], which is widely used in rubber reinforcement and pigment production. When molten NaCl – KCl is combined with iron, the process favors the production of graphitic carbon [41], a material of interest for applications in batteries, electrodes, and other electronic components due to its high conductivity and structural stability. Thermal plasma and microwave plasma, predominantly produce carbon black during plasma methane pyrolysis in the

Table 2

Comparison of carbon materials produced using different methane pyrolysis methods.

Pyrolysis technology	Catalyst	Carbon type	Ref
Thermal catalysis	Fe-based catalysts	CNTs and CNFs	[39]
Molten salts	Molten gallium	Carbon black	[40]
Molten salts	Molten NaCl-KCl with Fe	Graphitic carbon	[41]
Thermal plasma	None	Carbon black	[42]
Microwave plasma	None	Carbon black	[32]
Dielectric barrier discharge	NiO/Al ₂ O ₃	CNFs	[43]
Gliding arc plasma	None	Graphite, graphene, MWCNTs, carbon black	This work

absence of a catalyst [32,42]. While carbon black has broad industrial uses, it is typically considered a lower-value carbon product compared to CNTs and CNFs. Helen et al. reported the production of CNTs on a NiO/Al₂O₃ catalyst in non-oxidative methane conversion using a DBD reactor [43]. Notably, this work, using a GA reactor, can produce a diverse range of carbon materials such as graphite, graphene, MWCNTs, and carbon black without the use of a catalyst. This versatility makes GA plasma an appealing method for carbon material synthesis. In particular, MWCNTs are highly sought after for their excellent mechanical properties and are used in various high-performance applications, including nanocomposites, molecular storage, and (bio)sensors [39,40]. Moreover, because this process does not require a catalyst, it avoids the challenges of catalyst deactivation and the need to separate carbon from the catalyst, which are common in catalytic pyrolysis methods.

Overall, the GA-based methane pyrolysis process produced hydrogen with high selectivity and valuable carbon materials. The model accurately predicted the experimental results despite the complex nature of the plasma chemistry involved in this process. Although the modeling results are slightly sensitive to temperature changes (see Figure S5 in SI), they demonstrate the ability and reliability of the model to capture the essential plasma chemistry features in GA-based methane pyrolysis, making it a valuable tool for elucidating the underlying reaction mechanisms.

3.2. Calculation of key species densities

To gain insight into the underlying mechanism of GA-based methane pyrolysis, we performed a detailed analysis of key species in GA. In the GA, CH₄ undergoes initial activation through collisions with energetic electrons, leading to the formation of various reactive species, including CH₄⁺ and CH_x (x = 1–3) radicals and vibrationally excited CH₄ molecules. These reactive species subsequently react with each other to form the final products. The distribution of these reactive species is significantly influenced by the reduced electric field, which plays a critical role in controlling the distribution of electron energy deposition and the formation of active species.

Fig. 4 shows the electron energy loss fractions for a pure CH₄ discharge across different *E/N* values, with the gray area representing the *E/N* range investigated in our simulations (40–200 Td). Below 40 Td, the vibrational excitation of CH₄ is the predominant mechanism for electron energy deposition. Within the *E/N* range we studied, more CH₄

Fig. 4. Fractions of plasma energy deposited into different activation modes in pure CH₄ discharge mode across different *E/N* values, with the gray area representing the *E/N* range investigated in our simulations (40–200 Td). (ela: elastic; vib: vibrational excitation; dis: dissociation; ion: ionization).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 5. Calculated number densities of the most important species in the GA-based CH₄ pyrolysis system as a function of time during a single arc cycle (4.8 ms) and afterglow (a) excited species; (b) radicals; (c) final products (discharge power 45 W, CH₄ flow rate 4.5 L/min).

molecules are dissociated into CH_x ($x = 1-3$) radicals as the E/N increases. However, vibrational excitation remains a significant contributor to electron energy loss, decreasing from 98% at 40 Td to 50% at 200 Td. CH_4 ionization follows a similar trend to CH_4 dissociation but remains consistently below 4% for E/N values between 40 and 200 Td due to the higher threshold energy. Overall, the initial activation step in the methane pyrolysis process primarily involves the conversion of CH_4 into vibrational molecules and radicals. Elucidating the kinetic roles of these vibrationally excited molecules and radicals is crucial for obtaining a comprehensive understanding of the overall reaction mechanisms governing methane pyrolysis within a GA system.

To elucidate the underlying reaction mechanisms in GA-based CH_4 pyrolysis, Fig. 5 presents the time-dependent evolution of key species (excited species, radicals, and stable products) during CH_4 pyrolysis at a flow rate of 4.5 L/min and a discharge power of 45 W.

The initial activation step involves the formation of vibrationally excited $\text{CH}_4(v)$, represented by the stretching ($\text{CH}_4(v13)$) and bending ($\text{CH}_4(v24)$) vibrational modes resulting from electron impact collisions with CH_4 molecules. These excited states reach a peak number density of approximately $3 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ within 0.2 μs . Simultaneously, within the first 0.1 μs , a significant increase in the number density of vibrationally excited $\text{H}_2(v)$ was observed. Notably, $\text{H}_2(v1)$ exhibits a considerably higher density than $\text{H}_2(v2)$ and $\text{H}_2(v3)$, exceeding them by one and two orders of magnitude, respectively. By 0.1 ms, the combined density of these excited H_2 states surpasses that of $\text{CH}_4(v)$ despite a lower ground state density for H_2 , establishing them as the dominant excited species. This dominance can be attributed to the more efficient quenching of $\text{CH}_4(v)$ back to its ground state through collisions with heavy particles [44]. Vibrationally excited molecules can effectively lower activation energies compared to their ground states, accelerating the reaction process. For instance, the chain reaction involving $\text{CH}_4(v13)$ and H atoms ($\text{CH}_4(v13) + \text{H} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3 + \text{H}_2$) proceeds with a rate coefficient

approximately two orders of magnitude faster than that of its ground-state counterpart ($\text{CH}_4 + \text{H} \rightarrow \text{CH}_3 + \text{H}_2$). This substantial enhancement highlights the critical role of excited species such as $\text{CH}_4(v)$ and $\text{H}_2(v)$ in accelerating reactions, particularly when significant activation barriers are present.

A higher reduced electric field (E/N) led to increased dissociation of CH_4 into CH_x ($x = 1-3$) radicals. While their densities remained lower than those of the final products and excited species, these radicals played a critical role in NTP-based methane pyrolysis. Due to their high reactivity, they actively interact with other species, driving reactants through sequential steps toward product formation. Initially, CH_x ($x = 1-3$) and H radicals emerged as the dominant species and formed directly from CH_4 dissociation via electron impact collisions. The H atom density is slightly lower than that of CH_3 due to the formation of H_2 molecules through H atom recombination. Throughout the discharge, the densities of CH_3 , CH_2 , and H radicals exhibited a consistent trend, increasing up to $\sim 1 \mu\text{s}$, followed by a slight decrease. In contrast, the concentration of CH radicals initially decreased before returning to its initial level. The number density of C remained relatively stable, fluctuating at approximately 10^{11} cm^{-3} throughout the reaction. Notably, the primary C_2 -related radical C_2H_3 emerged after 0.2 μs , suggesting potential coupling reactions involving C_1 radicals. The subsequent emergence of another C_2 -related radicals, C_2 and C_2H , at a considerably later stage indicated a distinct formation mechanism. Additionally, C_3 -related radicals (C_3H_3 , C_3H_5 , and C_3H_7) appeared only after 2 μs .

Except for C_2H_6 , all the significant byproducts steadily increased in number density, reaching a steady state during the afterglow phase. H_2 exhibited a relatively steady increase, eventually becoming one of the most abundant species. C_2H_4 initially dominated as the primary carbon-containing molecule, but C_2H_6 surpassed C_2H_4 after 8 μs due to a faster formation rate. However, beyond a residence time of 10 ms, the density of C_2H_6 decreased moderately, with C_2H_2 becoming the primary C_2

Fig. 6. Reaction path flux analysis for CH_4 , H_2 , C, C_2 , and C_2H_2 during GA-assisted CH_4 pyrolysis at a discharge power of 45 W and a CH_4 flow rate of 4.5 L/min. (Blue lines: electron impact reactions; orange lines: reactions involving excited species; red lines: chain/chemical reactions; black lines: deposition reactions.).

hydrocarbon. Despite a time delay, solid carbon follows a similar trend to C_2H_2 , suggesting a strong correlation between the two, which will be described in Section 3.3.

3.3. Underlying plasma mechanism in methane pyrolysis with GA

Section 3.2 presents an overview of the temporal evolution of densities for key species. This section delves deeper into the underlying plasma mechanisms by analyzing the formation and loss pathways for crucial species such as CH_4 , C, H_2 , and C_2H_2 under specific operating conditions: a CH_4 flow rate of 4.5 L/min and a discharge power of 45 W.

3.3.1. Loss and formation processes of CH_4 and H_2

Fig. 6(a) illustrates the relative contributions of the primary loss and formation processes of CH_4 , offering a quantitative basis for analyzing the methane conversion mechanism. The chain-branching reaction $CH_4 + H \rightarrow CH_3 + H_2$ is the dominant pathway for loss of CH_4 in GA, accounting for 37.7% of the CH_4 conversion. Electron impact dissociation is a secondary pathway for CH_4 loss, contributing 26.3% to CH_4 consumption. These findings align with observations from other warm CH_4 plasmas (microwave plasma and GA) [6,45]. However, this contrasts with cold plasmas (DBD, RF discharge) [10,23], where electron impact dissociation, $e + CH_4 \rightarrow e + CH_3 + H$, typically dominates CH_4 loss. This discrepancy arises from the lower electron energy and higher gas temperature during GA discharge. In contrast to GA, DBD typically operates at a higher reduced electrical field (>200 Td) [46], resulting in a greater mean electron energy (4–7 eV) than that of GA (1–2 eV), which enhances electron impact dissociation [46]. Moreover, the elevated temperature within the GA enhances methane dissociation through collisions with heavy particles by overcoming significant activation barriers. For example, the dominant CH_4 -consuming reaction $CH_4 + H \rightarrow CH_3 + H_2$ exhibits a strong temperature dependence, with its rate constant increasing significantly from 1.8×10^{-19} cm³/s to 2.42×10^{-13} cm³/s as the gas temperature increases from 300 K to 1000 K. Based on the kinetic results, optimizing the reactor design to maintain high reaction temperatures can directly increase hydrogen production by promoting the chain-branching reaction $CH_4 + H \rightarrow CH_3 + H_2$. However, excessively high temperatures may shift the discharge mode to thermal plasma, resulting in undesirable energy losses. Therefore, maintaining moderate reaction temperatures is crucial for achieving optimal energy efficiency.

Recombination reactions primarily drive CH_4 formation. The total rate of CH_4 formation was only approximately 30% lower than the total rate of CH_4 loss, indicating that a substantial portion of the CH_3 radicals recombined to form CH_4 . This significant recombination of CH_3 radicals, either with hydrogen ($CH_3 + H \rightarrow CH_4$) or other radicals, such as C_2H_5 , to produce CH_4 and C_2H_4 underscores the dynamic equilibrium maintained within plasma environments.

Hydrogen is a key product of NTP-based methane pyrolysis, and its efficient production is vital for the commercial viability of this process. Fig. 6(b) illustrates the main reactions involved in hydrogen formation and loss, providing a foundation for this analysis [6]. A strong correlation exists between hydrogen production and methane conversion. Both reactions were primarily driven by the same key reaction, $CH_4 + H \rightarrow CH_3 + H_2$, which contributed 44.2% to hydrogen formation and 37.7% to CH_4 depletion. In alignment with observations for CH_4 conversion, these results are consistent with findings in GAs but contrast with those reported in DBDs and RF discharges [6,37]. Electron impact dissociation also contributes to hydrogen formation, particularly through interactions with CH_4 , C_2H_4 , and C_2H_6 . These pathways account for 8.4%, 14.4%, and 8.3% of H_2 formation, respectively. Dicarbon (C_2) plays a significant role in hydrogen loss, with the reaction $C_2 + H_2 \rightarrow C_2H + H$ being the major pathway, accounting for 40.8% of the total hydrogen consumption. Subsequently, the reaction of the C_2H radical with additional hydrogen ($C_2H + H_2 \rightarrow C_2H_2 + H$) contributes another 28.5% of the total hydrogen loss. Overall, C_2 -involved reactions account for approximately 70% of the total hydrogen loss. Additionally, electron

impact dissociation, $e + H_2 \rightarrow e + H + H$ and $e + H_2 \rightarrow e + H_2(v)$, was significant, contributing 14.8% and 8.1%, respectively, to H_2 consumption.

3.3.2. Loss and formation processes of C and C_2

Solid carbon is one of the most important products of GA-assisted methane pyrolysis, accounting for 24.4% of the selectivity. These carbon materials are considered attractive for a range of promising industrial applications, such as battery anodes, fillers, and biosensors. Therefore, a particular focus was placed on elucidating the mechanism of solid carbon formation in our simulations.

The simulations indicate that solid carbons are produced through the condensation of C and C_2 radicals after their generation via hydrocarbon dehydration (mainly C_2H_2 and C_2H_4). The overall contribution of C radicals to solid carbon formation remains limited, accounting for only 5.0% of the total formation, while C_2 radicals are significantly more influential (~95.0%). Fig. 6(c) depicts the primary pathways for the formation and loss of C radicals, along with their corresponding contributions. The electron impact dissociation of hydrocarbons constitutes the primary mechanism for C radical generation, accounting for 99.9% of the total C formation. Specifically, C_2H_2 serves as the primary precursor for C radicals (72.3% of total C radical production) through the reaction $e + C_2H_2 \rightarrow e + C + CH_2$, while C_2H_4 contributes 26.0% of the total C radical production via the reaction $e + C_2H_4 \rightarrow e + C + CH_4$. In contrast to initial expectations, CH_4 , despite its abundance, plays a minimal role in C radical formation. The limited contribution of CH_4 to carbon radical formation compared to that of C_2 hydrocarbons can be attributed to its structurally stable nature. Dissociation of CH_4 into carbon radicals necessitates a considerably higher threshold energy (~12.0 eV) than the significantly lower activation energies required for C_2H_2 and C_2H_4 (5.1 eV and 3.8 eV, respectively) [44]. The greater proportion of C_2H_2 relative to C_2H_4 , coupled with its lower activation energy compared to that of CH_4 , positions it as a more effective contributor to carbon formation in this process. Due to the low activation barrier of C_2H_2 , many plasma-based carbon synthesis processes use C_2H_2 as a precursor [47]. However, the cost of C_2H_2 can make these processes economically less attractive. In addition to electron impact dissociation, a minor fraction of C radicals is generated through chain-branching reactions, such as $CH + H \rightarrow C + H_2$. These reactions, though they play a significant role in thermal methane pyrolysis, are less prevalent in plasma processes.

Fig. 7(a) shows the temporal evolution of the reaction rates for the C radical generation reactions. The formation of C radicals through electron impact dissociation exhibits a time-dependent increasing trend, particularly for reactions involving C_2H_2 and C_2H_4 . This trend is attributed to the increasing population of these hydrocarbons with reaction time. Initially, the dissociation of CH_4 was predominant due to its higher concentration, but its contribution diminished over time. The initially significant contribution of CH_4 can be ascribed to the enhanced electric field resulting from decreased conductivity at the start of discharge [48]. This condition produces more energetic electrons, shifting energy dissipation from electron impact excitation to electron impact dissociation, thus improving the production efficiency of carbon radicals. The primary pathway for C radical loss involves collisions with vibrationally excited $H_2(v)$, which accounts for most of the C radical consumption (94.7%). The significance of this reaction increases over time, paralleling the increase in $H_2(v)$ production. Among these reactions, $C + H_2(v2) \rightarrow CH + H$ emerges as the most critical, with a relative contribution of 84.1%, facilitated by the sufficient vibrational energy provided by $H_2(v2)$ to overcome the activation energy barrier. Although $H_2(v1)$ and $H_2(v3)$ also participate, their impacts are less significant due to insufficient energy (0.55 eV for $H_2(v1)$) or a lower population ($H_2(v3)$).

The important role of C_2 in carbon material growth, particularly in the formation of critical nuclei, has been reported in the literature [49–51]. Optical emission spectroscopy (OES) measurements clearly

(a)

(a)

(b)

(b)

Fig. 7. Time-dependent evolution of reaction rates for key (a) formation processes and (b) loss processes of C at a discharge power of 45 W and a CH₄ flow rate of 4.5 L/min.

revealed the characteristic emission lines of C₂ dimers (515 and 560 nm), especially in regions proximate to the growth substrate of carbon materials [31]. The empirical calculations proposed by Gruen further corroborated the significant role of C₂ in the evolution of critical nuclei into carbon materials [52]. In our simulations, C₂ radicals were also identified as the major contributors to solid carbon formation, accounting for 95.0% of the total formation.

Fig. 6(d) illustrates the main pathways for the formation and loss of C₂ radicals, along with their relative contributions. Like C generation, the formation of C₂ radicals is primarily facilitated through electron impact dissociation of C₂H₂ ($e + C_2H_2 \rightarrow e + C_2 + H_2$ and $e + C_2H_2 \rightarrow e + C_2 + 2H$), accounting for approximately 99.9% of the total C₂ radical production. A comparative analysis of the formation mechanisms for C and C₂ revealed that C₂H₂ is more readily converted into a C₂ radical. Fig. 6(e) demonstrates that 26.6% of C₂H₂ undergoes conversion to C₂,

Fig. 8. Time-dependent evolution of reaction rates for key (a) formation processes and (b) loss processes of C₂ at a discharge power of 45 W and a CH₄ flow rate of 4.5 L/min.

whereas a smaller fraction (10.9%) leads to C radical formation. The efficiency of C₂H₂ as a precursor for the C₂ radical over C can be attributed to its robust acetylenic C≡C bond with a bond energy of 8.7 eV, in contrast to the C–H bond energy of 4.29 eV. Therefore, the structure of C₂H₂ preferentially favors hydrogen loss to form C₂ radicals rather than cleavage of the C≡C bond to yield C and CH radicals. Fig. 8 shows the temporal evolution of the reaction rates for the generation and consumption pathways of C₂ radicals. Chain-branching reactions, including $CH + C \rightarrow C_2 + H$ and $C + C \rightarrow C_2$, also contribute to the formation of C₂ radicals. Although their overall contribution is minor, collisions of C radicals and other radicals serve as the primary channel for C₂ formation during the initial stage of GA-based methane pyrolysis. However, with increasing residence time, the concentration of C₂H₂ increases, enhancing the rate of electron impact on C₂H₂

dissociation. As a result, C_2 production from C_2H_2 dissociation surpasses chain-branching reactions by 5–6 orders of magnitude. Regarding C_2 radical loss mechanisms, the primary pathway for C_2 consumption involves collisions with H_2 , accounting for a significant 72.9% of the total C_2 loss. This process is closely followed by the deposition of C_2 radicals, which constitute 26.2% of its consumption. Additionally, a minor fraction of the C_2 radicals is converted through interactions with various ionic species, including H^+ , CH_5^+ , and H_2^+ . Although less significant, those ionic reactions play a notable role in the overall dynamics of C_2 loss.

Through simulations, electron impact dissociation of C_2H_2 was identified as the dominant pathway for C and C_2 radical generation, with the subsequent collision of these radicals with H_2 or $H_2(v)$ being a significant loss mechanism. Therefore, H_2 is often used to reduce carbon deposition in plasma-assisted methane coupling to higher hydrocarbons [53].

3.3.3. Loss and formation processes of C_2H_2

C_2H_2 serves as a primary precursor for carbon radical formation, positioning it as a critical intermediate in the conversion of CH_4 to solid carbon. This section outlines the formation and loss mechanisms of C_2H_2 derived from extensive simulations to provide insights into optimizing carbon material synthesis.

Fig. 6(e) shows the primary processes involved in the loss and generation of C_2H_2 . One of the significant pathways for C_2H_2 formation is the electron impact dissociation of C_2H_4 , accounting for 36.6% of its production. This process highlights the role of energetic electrons in facilitating the breakdown of C_2H_4 into C_2H_2 , demonstrating the

efficiency of plasma in driving complex chemical reactions. Zhang et al. [9] reported a similar mechanism in a CH_4/N_2 GA plasma, where electron and excited nitrogen species interactions with C_2H_4 contributed significantly to C_2H_2 formation. In contrast, Heijkers et al. highlighted neutral dissociation reactions of C_2H_3 as the most important processes in C_2H_2 formation [10]. This discrepancy might be attributed to the substantially higher plasma power (224 W) and reaction temperature (3000–6000 K) used in their work. Another crucial channel for C_2H_2 formation involves chain-branching reactions of C_2H , specifically the recombination of C_2H radicals with other species, such as CH_4 , H_2 , and C_2H_4 , contributing to 50.4% of C_2H_2 formation. Among these interactions, the interaction between C_2H and CH_4 was most noteworthy, representing 34.4% of the total C_2H_2 formation. While C_2H radicals significantly contribute to the formation of C_2H_2 , 46.8% of C_2H_2 also dissociated back into C_2H upon collision with electrons, indicating complex equilibrium between C_2H_2 formation and loss. Consequently, the net contribution of C_2H to C_2H_2 is less significant than the direct electron impact dissociation of C_2H_4 into C_2H_2 . Moreover, a substantial portion (36.7%) of C_2H_2 is converted into C and C_2 radicals, which further participate in the formation of solid carbon.

3.3.4. Overall reaction pathways

The overall plasma chemistry is schematically outlined in Fig. 9 to provide deeper insights into the underlying reaction mechanisms in GA-assisted methane pyrolysis. The reaction sequence is initiated by the electron impact dissociation of CH_4 , which breaks CH_4 down into CH_x ($x = 1-3$) and H radicals. H atoms react quickly with CH_4 in a GA plasma

Fig. 9. Network of GA-based methane pyrolysis in pure CH_4 at a discharge power of 45 W and a CH_4 flow rate of 4.5 L/min. (Blue lines: electron impact reactions; orange lines: reactions involving excited species; red lines: chain/chemical reactions; black lines: deposition reactions).

where the gas temperature is high, enhancing the conversion of CH₄ significantly.

The CH₃ radicals produced from the initial conversion of CH₄ are crucial for the formation of various C₂ hydrocarbons, including C₂H₂, C₂H₄, and C₂H₆, through recombination reactions. Fig. 9 shows a clear pathway from C₂H₆ to C₂H₄ to C₂H₂, with negligible reverse reactions, leading to a selectivity order of C₂H₂ > C₂H₄ > C₂H₆. Electron impact reactions play a pivotal role in the further breakdown of these hydrocarbons, with C₂H₂ potentially dehydrating to C₂ and C radicals, which subsequently form solid carbon. An optimal electron energy distribution can be achieved by controlling operating parameters, such as discharge power, flow rate, and reactor structure to boost solid carbon production and control the quality of carbon materials.

Additionally, interactions between C₂H₅, C₂H₄, and C₂H₂ hydrocarbons and CH_x (x = 1–3) radicals facilitate the production of C₃H_x (x = 3, 5, 7) radicals. Fig. 9 depicts the formation pathway of C₃ hydrocarbons, which predominantly progresses from C₃H₄ to C₃H₆ and ultimately to C₃H₈, with negligible reverse reactions. Therefore, C₃H₈ has the highest concentration among all the C₃ hydrocarbons.

4. Conclusions

A comprehensive chemical kinetic analysis was conducted to elucidate the underlying reaction mechanisms governing methane pyrolysis into hydrogen and solid carbon in a GA reactor, with a particular emphasis on the formation of carbon species. A 0D chemical kinetics model was developed to simulate the plasma chemistry involved in this process, including electron impact reactions and reactions involving excited species, ions and heavy species. To accurately represent the formation of solid carbon, the model incorporated two types of carbon species, C and C₂ radicals, along with 53 carbon-related reactions. The model also accounts for carbon deposition, assuming that once carbon undergoes condensation, it is effectively shielded from plasma-induced decomposition.

Model validation was achieved by comparing simulation results with experimental data on methane conversion and product selectivity under varying input power and flow rate conditions. The model successfully captured the primary trends in methane conversion, demonstrating reasonable agreement and therefore confirming the accuracy of the plasma kinetic model.

The simulation results revealed a strong correlation between hydrogen production and methane conversion, predominantly driven by the key reaction CH₄ + H → CH₃ + H₂. This reaction accounts for 44.2% of the total hydrogen formation and 37.7% of the total CH₄ consumption. Although electron impact dissociations of CH₄ are significant in DBDs, they play a secondary role in GA-based methane pyrolysis due to the lower reduced electric field.

Carbon (C) and dicarbon (C₂) radicals are identified as crucial elements in the formation of solid carbon. C₂ radicals, in particular, are the primary contributors to solid carbon formation and account for 95.0 % of the total carbon yield due to the relatively low C–H dissociation energy. The majority of solid carbon originates from the electron impact dissociation of C₂H₂ through the reactions e + C₂H₂ → e + C₂ + H₂/2H followed by subsequent C₂ condensation. Interestingly, despite the generation of numerous C radicals from C₂H₂, the majority (94.7%) are transformed into CH radicals through collisions with vibrationally excited H₂(v). This study elucidates the complex reaction pathways involved in GA-based methane pyrolysis, revealing the critical role of C₂ radicals in solid carbon formation and the dominant influence of hydrogen on methane conversion.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Xuchu Yuan: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Jintao Sun:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation,

Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Yichen Ma:** Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Yaolin Wang:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology. **Bowen Liu:** Validation, Methodology. **Yuxiang Cai:** Writing – review & editing. **Xue Yong:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Xin Tu:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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